

Musical instruments in class singing: Confusion between musical functions and giving signals for classroom management

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Abstract

The use of musical instruments (MI) and audio devices (AD) is an integral part of the practice of teaching and learning singing at school. Songs can be taught without MI or AD as the human voice suffices for singing. Yet, MI and AD are a tacit part of song teaching. What is their role and how do teachers use them?

The aim of this study is to investigate the actual use of musical instruments and audio devices among pre-service generalist teachers. This is still an unexplored field in music didactic. This study pursues a phenomenological approach to the analysis of videotaped lessons, lesson-based interviews, and personalised open-ended questionnaires collected longitudinally during the three years of teacher training. In this paper, I present the analysis of selected moments from three lessons of a pre-service generalist during the three years of training. The analysis shows the diverse use of AD and MI and reveals that it is not only a question of developing the skills needed to play a full accompaniment to singing, but also of using MI and AD in interaction with children to convey to them fundamental components of cultural musical practice.

Keywords

Musical instrument; audio device; pre-service generalist teacher; music didactic; class singing.

Introduction

To understand the use of MI and AD in the practice of class singing, it is important to identify when and how they are integrated by generalists. This is a way to gain knowledge about how the practice works and how it can be improved. The practice of class singing led by generalists is still little explored in music didactic. Even more so is the study of the specific competence to use MI and AD as music didactic tools. Some studies have focused on the use of specific musical instruments in general music classes, such as the ukulele and xylophone used for singing and introduction to music theory (Davis, 2004; Giebelhausen, 2016). The aim of my research is to obtain an overview of the possibilities of using MI and AD in generalist-led classroom singing to identify and define potential patterns. In this paper, I present the case study of the pre-service teacher 'Lily'. The analysis of this case study showed how Lily embedded percussion instruments (shakers and rattles) and body percussion in her first- and second-year lessons, and piano in the third year. Lily used percussion instruments and body percussion for different and varied purposes. In the first year, the likelihood of Lily's use of a AD to learn the target song was based on the acceleration of tempo when Lily sang a cappella in the lesson. This acceleration was very close to that of the original recording (AD). However, the attempt to reproduce the song as heard from the AD represented a difficulty in managing the many simultaneous activities while leading the class. The use of the piano in the last lesson demonstrates Lily's determination to put into practice her skills of instrumental accompaniment to the song, which she developed during her training.

Method

The overall study concerns the analysis of ten pre-service generalist teachers who used AD and different MI during class singing (guitar, percussion/body percussion, piano). For each teacher, the data corpus consists of three videotaped lessons, three lesson-based interviews and a personalised open-ended questionnaire. This article focuses on the video analysis. All the videos in the study were transcribed using the LAMap methodology (Savona et al., 2021), which graphically represents the course of the actions and activities of the whole lessons and enables researchers to systematically describe and analyse selected moments based on epistemological interests. The selected lesson moments presented in this paper were analysed acoustically and microgenetically (Valsiner, 2017).

Analysis and results

In this section, I first present Lily's three lessons as a whole and then focus on analysing the moments in the lessons where Lily used MI or AD.

Figure 1. Lesson Activities Map of Lily's three internship lessons (Savona, 2022)

Figure 1 shows the LAMaps of Lily's three lessons, which were videotaped once a year. This allows us to systematically describe and analyse individual actions and/or activities while considering the overall original context. In the LAMap, the simultaneity of actions and activities is organised vertically into 'episodes'. In Figure 1, the lessons episodes in which Lily used musical instruments are highlighted. In the first lesson, Lily used shakers and integrated body percussion (episodes 1.1-1.4). In the second lesson she used rattles (episodes 2.1-2.7), and in the third lesson the piano (episode 3.1). Below I show the detailed description and analysis of these episodes.

First-year lesson: Getting prepared with a AD and leading song, semantic gestures, shakers, and body percussion simultaneously

In this lesson, Lily and the children were seated in a circle. Lily's supervisor also participated in the activity and was part of the circle. The lesson took place in the usual classroom where Lily had prepared percussion instruments next to her chair. In this lesson, MIs were used in three episodes (in Figure 1: 1.2, 1.3, 1.4) but on the LAMap we can see that Lily used a AD at the beginning of the lesson. She wanted the children to listen to an instrumental piece to dance and make free movements. Lily did not use the AD to play the target song and in later episodes she only used MIs. However, I mean to describe and analyse episode 1.1 to reflect on the teacher's use of ADs during lesson preparation.

In this episode, Lily sang and staged the song a cappella while simultaneously trying to look at the cards to read the lyrics and maintain eye contact with the children. One aspect of this episode is interesting: the speed with which Lily performed the song suggests that she used a AD to prepare for the lesson.

Figure 2. Analysis of the performance tempo of the edited song version and Lily's performance in class (Savona, 2022)

Figure 2 shows the comparison between the analysis of the song speed on the AD and Lily's performance. The song consists of 3 verses organised into 24 bars. The analysis of the AD version shows that the song starts with a tempo of 88 bpm and ends with 180 bpm. Hence, the song on the AD is performed with a progressive acceleration from the first to the last verse. Acoustic analysis of Lily's performance a cappella shows that she started singing at 70 bpm and finished at 146 bpm. In this way, she reproduced the tempo acceleration of the AD version. Although she sang everything slightly more slowly than the AD, Lily's performance tempo had become so fast that she could not control the simultaneity of her actions, and the song flow was interrupted. The analysis of this episode shows that the use of a AD served as a model for Lily. The use of a AD requires teachers to reflect on and evaluate whether some musical features of the recorded version should be omitted or adapted according to their skills and the lesson goals.

In episodes 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4, Lily divided the group of children into four sub-groups and assigned each one a specific activity. The children in the first sub-group had to tap two fingers on the chair (body percussion). The second sub-group had the task of making semantic gestures. The third one had to sing together with Lily, and the fourth one to play the shakers. Lily explained to the children in the fourth sub-group that they had to play their shakers when she played the rattle.

When Lily started singing, the children in the first sub-group started tapping their fingers on their chairs when the class teacher (Lily's supervisor) sitting next to them showed them the movement and started first. When Lily shook the rattle, the fourth sub-group played the shakers, but the children's reaction was delayed because Lily's movement was unexpected. At the same time, Lily sang, shook the rattle, and demonstrated semantic gestures. Her singing was interrupted because Lily was also looking at the cards with the lyrics. At the end of this episode, Lily repeated the song, redistributing the tasks among the sub-groups.

The analysis of these three episodes makes us reflect on the goals of a class singing lesson and the reasons for using percussion instruments and body percussion in this context. The main goal of the lesson is to teach a new song. The use of percussion could be considered secondary. However, when integrated into the lesson, the use of percussion promotes the development of sensory-motor and listening skills and transmits to the children one of the fundamental characteristics of sound, that is, its timing patterns. Exploring the use of percussion helps introduce children to understand and produce temporal features such as long and short, and strong and weak sounds. Structuring the lesson activities progressively facilitates the development of the skills needed to play instruments correctly to deliver their effective use. On the LAMap we see that Lily never recited the text only while playing. If she had done so, she would have given a chance to the children to experience the way the metre played by the instrument is combined with the metre of the lyrics. This, as well as other instructional strategies, would have helped to avoid overloading Lily with simultaneous activities and would have enhanced the children's musical experience.

Second-year lesson: Multifunctional rattles

The second lesson took place in the music classroom where there was a piano and a stereo. A xylophone, wooden sticks and rattles were arranged on the floor. Lily sat with the children in a circle. In episodes 2.1 to 2.7, Lily and the children used the rattles in different ways which I analyse in detail below.

In episode 2.1, Lily asked the children to close their eyes and took the xylophone stick. Before returning to the children, Lily replaced the stick with rattles. Lily told the children to listen attentively, then she played the rattles and sang the target song a cappella. When she stopped singing, Lily played the rattles again and told the children to open their eyes.

In episode 2.2, Lily explained to the children that "a song always has an introduction" and asked them to remember what she had done at the beginning of the lesson. One child exclaimed "the bell!", referring to the rattle Lily had played. This answer seemed to be what Lily had expected. She gave rattles to two children and asked them to stand next to her. Lily explained that when they played the rattles, she and the other children would sing and make the semantic gestures. Then, when the song was finished, they had to play the rattles one more time. Episodes 2.3 to 2.6 are repetitions in which a new pair of children followed Lily's instructions to use the rattles. Each time, Lily counted "1, 2, 3", the children played the rattles, and she sang and made semantic gestures with the others. Yet, at the end of each episode, none of the children played the rattles because Lily did not give them a sign.

In episode 2.7, Lily asked the children to close their eyes. Each child could leave the classroom when she or he heard the rattle next to the ear. So, Lily played the rattle for each child until they had all left the music class.

By saying "a song always has an introduction", Lily explicitly presented the 'introduction' as an obligatory part of a song. Usually, it provides pitch, metre, and tempo (Stadler Elmer, 2015). In fact, in these episodes Lily had intended to use the rattles as an introductory means. However, it was the upbeat sung by Lily that actually provided the starting pitch for the children. It seems that Lily did not yet know that the rattles, due to the organological peculiarities, are not appropriate for introducing the necessary musical features for singing together (Sachs, 1914; Reinhard, 2021). The rattles are:

- a. indirectly shaken idiophones whose sound is produced by an internal ball beating against the wall of the metal body. Since the ball has a certain latency in the instrument, the rattle player must learn to anticipate the movement to control and achieve correct timing. Thus, the proper shaking of the instrument requires the development of fine sensory-motor control. This can be quite difficult for children, especially if they are not deliberately instructed. Hence, the lack of knowledge on this instrument and of instructional skills has led to the misunderstanding of a proper use of the rattles.
- b. instruments without a stable pitch that cannot be used to provide a reference for pitch and tonality. Therefore, the rattles are inappropriate for giving the starting pitch for singing. At this point it is worth highlighting a detail from episode 2.1. Before singing the song for the first time, Lily had taken the xylophone stick but then replaced it with rattles. How would it have been different if Lily had used the xylophone in the same way she used the rattles? The xylophone is a direct percussion idiophone because the sound is produced by striking the sticks on the instrument. Setting the metre and tempo with the xylophone could have been more effective because hitting would have produced one beat at time, well defined and without latency. For children, the movement to produce patterns of periodic sounds would have been easier. In addition, the xylophone is a fixed sound instrument. The children could have played the starting pitch and prepared the tonality.

The analysis of these episodes demonstrates how the inexperienced use of the MI led to the 'de-functionalisation' of the introduction. Lily's use of the rattles served solely as a signal for attention. In the instruction preceding the series of repetitions, Lily asked the children to play the rattles at the end of the song as well, but no one did so because Lily did not give them a signal. This indicates that the rattles did not have a function at all, and even Lily had forgotten about them. Episode 2.1 had shown how Lily combined the rattles with the verbal instruction to reopen the eyes after listening carefully to the song. In episode 2.7, Lily played the rattle near each child's ear to signal them to leave the room. In both cases she used the rattles to indicate a closure. In this lesson, Lily encouraged the exploring of rattles and combined them with a variety of didactic and theoretical music instructions. The use of rattles to indicate preparation and closure was successful, while the use of rattles musically to prepare pitch, metre and tempo was not effective.

Third-year lesson. New experience with self-accompaniment on the piano

In this lesson, Lily and the children were seated in a circle. In the classroom there was an upright piano, positioned with its back towards the circle. Episode 3.1 is the only one in which Lily played the piano. Once the lesson started, Lily asked the children to close their eyes and then went to the piano. She played an introduction and then sang the target song while continuing to play. When she finished singing and playing, Lily returned to the children, told them to open their eyes and asked, "what did you hear?". By this, she drew their attention to the lyrics' semantic content and moved on to work on them.

For the first time in her internship, Lily sang a song while accompanying herself on the piano. This demonstrates a noticeable step in her professional development of skills as Lily had only started studying piano two years earlier as part of her teacher training.

Figure 3. Analysis of the first time Lily accompanied herself while singing in class (Savona, 2022)

Figure 3 shows the analysis of this episode in which we can identify early abilities to handle the simultaneity of playing and singing, i.e., to coordinate the singing voice with the reading of the song's score, and with performing the chords correctly and in time. Fig. 3 displays the score of the song's edited version, with melody and chords. Below it, the temporal structure of the song is displayed, which consists of three verses of 8 bars each. The comparison of Lily's performance with the sheet music shows that she had no difficulty in bars 1, 3, 4, 5 and 8. Yet, the flow of the song was disturbed in bars 2 and 6 of every verse. Here, Lily needed more time to play the A7, G and A chords, and sometimes she played correctly and sometimes not. The wrong chord in bar 7 may have happened accidentally in the second verse. The omission of the D/A and A chords in bar 8 (first beat) may have been planned as Lily continued to play and sing with confidence and the song flow was not influenced. While playing, Lily sang the melody in a stable manner.

Conclusions

This study explored the use of musical instruments (MI) and audio devices (AD) as part of the practice of teaching songs in class within the context of pre-service generalist teacher education. This area of research represents a combination of pedagogical means and learning objectives that deserves further investigation. Detailed graphic and verbal descriptions of pre-service generalist Lily's case study revealed that the use of MI and AD provides a rich source of information about the instruments themselves, the knowledge a teacher implicitly conveys through manipulation, and the quality of musical interaction with children. Analyses showed that Lily in her final year of training was still exploring the many facets of teaching songs and therefore also the use of different MIs and ADs. This longitudinal and microgenetic study showed that the use of MI and AD is multi-referential: MI and AD do not necessarily and exclusively support singing which is still the main learning objective of the lesson. This article provides insights into a hitherto unexplored aspect of generalist teacher-led song leading and thus contributes to filling knowledge gaps in this domain.

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